

LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT AND COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT RESPONSE OF THIN PLY BASED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

E.V. González¹, A. Soto¹, P. Maimí¹, J.R. Sainz de Aja², F.M. de la Escalera², R. Olsson³ and E. Alvarez⁴

¹AMADE, Polytechnic School, University of Girona
Campus Montilivi s/n, 17071 Girona, Spain
Email: emilio.gonzalez@udg.edu, web page: <http://amade.udg.edu/>

²Aernnova Engineering Solutions Ibérica S.A., Structural Integrity Department
20 Manoteras Avenue – Building B, 5th Floor, 28050 Madrid, Spain
Email: joseramon.sainzdeaja@aernnova.com, web page: <http://www.aernnova.com/>

³Swerea SICOMP, Box 104, Mölndal, Sweden
Email: robin.olsson@swerea.se, web page: <http://www.swerea.se/sicomp/>

⁴Oxeon AB, Företagsgatan 24, Borås, Sweden
Email: elena.alvarez@textreme.com, web page: <http://oxeon.se/>

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ABSTRACT

The advantage of using thin plies is a well-known feature in laminated composite plates, since the homogenized properties usually improve, and in turn, the performance of the structure. In the literature, several works deal with the study of the ply thickness effect for different structures and loading conditions. However, fewer studies have been performed to understand the structure response under out-of-plane loading, such as the low-velocity impact event. The apparition of high quality manufactured ultra-thin plies, such as the composite material product TeXtreme® of Oxeon AB, requires a detailed analysis of their damage resistance and tolerance performance under impact loading. The present work deals with a discussion of a large experimental test campaign of drop-weight impact tests and Compression After Impact (CAI) tests on ultra-thin ply based composite laminates. The composite material analysed is a plain-weave fabric with HTS45 fibers and 20 mm wide yarns, used with HexFlow® RTM 6 mono-component epoxy system, and manufactured out-of-autoclave. Two ply thicknesses are considered: 0.08 mm and 0.16 mm. For each case, the same laminate thickness and stacking sequence is considered in order to define the same in-plane stiffness. The study considers different impact energy levels.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that the effect of reducing the ply thickness in polymer-based laminated structures results in improved homogenized ply properties, and thus in a better mechanical performance of the structure. When thin plies are used in a laminate, less manufacturing defects are likely to appear, and failure mechanisms such as matrix cracking and delamination are delayed at higher stresses, or even, do not occur in comparison to thick ply laminates [1]. This improvement in material properties can also be thought as a reduction in the structure weight, without sacrificing strength or stiffness.

A significant number of recent works have been published dealing with the analysis of the thickness effect on different material characterization tests and on other common tests that are usually performed on composite structures, e.g. open-hole compression test [2]. In most of the cases, the results demonstrate that the use of thin plies improves the structure response.

Concerning the particular case of the low-velocity impact test and the sequenced Compression After Impact (CAI) test for the corresponding assessment of the damage resistance and the damage tolerance of a plate, some works can also be found in the literature [2-6]. However, comparing the results published by each author, there is not an agreement regarding the effects of the ply thickness in plates subjected to these loading cases. The differences observed can be attributed to differences on the ply thicknesses used, which ranges from 0.03 mm until 0.72 mm.

The content of the present paper is an experimental study of drop-weight impact tests and Compression After Impact (CAI) tests on thin ply laminates. For the impact tests, different energy levels are considered and C-scan inspections are performed to detect the projected delamination areas after impact. These tests are performed on two type laminates, manufactured with different ply thicknesses. A short discussion of the results is performed in order to highlight the effect of the ply thickness under these loading conditions.

2 MATERIALS AND TEST SET-UP

2.1 Materials tested

The carbon fiber used in this study is Tenax® HTS45 with 12K filament yarn. The matrix is HexFlow® RTM 6 mono-component epoxy system, supplied by Hexcel®. The plies are presented as TeXtreme® plain weave with 20 mm wide yarn fabrics (see Fig. 1), manufactured by OXEON AB. Two ply thicknesses are considered: 0.08 mm and 0.16 mm (with 80 gsm and 160 gsm areal weights, respectively). In both cases, the fiber volume fraction is of 59 %. The method used to manufacture these thin plies is based on the spread-tow technology, at which conventional filament tows are thinned by increasing the tow width.

Figure 1: Weave pattern of the woven fabric used.

The laminates selected are quasi-isotropic, with conventional ply orientations: $[(45/-45) / (0/90)]_n$, where n is equal to 7 and 14 for 160 gsm and 80 gsm laminates, respectively (with the orientation 0° aligned with the major in-plane dimension, i.e. 150 mm); in the following, these laminates are respectively identified as IC160 and IC80. For both cases, the nominal laminate thickness is of 4.5 mm which is a common value for drop-weight impact laboratory coupons. These laminates are manufactured using Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process.

The study considers three different impact energy levels: 20, 30 and 40 J; for each case, the impactor mass is of 5 kg and a minimum sample of 3 specimens is considered.

2.2 Test set-ups

The tests were performed using a CEAST Fractovis Plus instrumented drop-weight tower, with a 16 mm diameter hemispherical impactor and an automatic anti-rebound impactor system. The specimens are placed over a flat support with a 125 mm by 75 mm rectangular cut-out and they are restrained during the impact by means of four rubber-tipped clamps, as suggested in ASTM D7136 standard test [7]. The impact tester is equipped with a load cell of 22 kN attached to the impactor.

Most of the tests performed were instrumented with a laser sensor type MEL M70LL series, to measure the displacement at the impact point of the back-face (non-impacted face). A white tape is glued on the back-face of the specimen to reduce the voltage noise and so to improve the measurement resolution. Using the back-face displacement and the displacement of the impactor (obtained by integrating twice the acceleration), the indentation suffered by the plate during the impact can be obtained approximately. Fig. 2 shows the clamping system used for the tests performed with the back-face displacement instrumentation. The impact velocity prior to impact is measured using an optical sensor. The synchronized test measurements are the impact load and the back-face displacement. The data acquisition system used is NI DAQ 6366 USB X-series (2 MHz, 16 bits, 64 MS internal memory).

Figure 2: Manual clamping fixture for impact test. The fixture is instrumented with a laser displacement sensor.

After the impact tests, ultrasonic C-scan technique inspections are performed to identify the projected delamination areas of the specimens. Finally, the CAI tests are performed using a MTS InsightTM Electromechanical tester with a 300 kN load cell and equipped with the common CAI clamping system reported in [8]. Three additional non-impacted specimens for each laminate are tested under compression to know the pristine compression strength.

3 IMPACT RESULTS

3.1 Drop-weight impact tests

In order to perform a manageable comparison of the impact test results, the mean values of the results for each laminate type and impact energy are calculated. The impact load versus time and the impact load versus the impactor displacement are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 for IC80 and IC160 laminates, respectively. As can be observed, characteristic impact load points are different for each material system. The threshold for the first load drop of IC80 is higher than for IC160. This result can be attributed to that the failure mechanisms in IC80 linked to this point are delayed to higher loads. Since matrix cracking in thin plies is reduced, and this matrix cracking can act as trigger for the delamination, the onset of the delamination is then delayed to higher loads.

On the other hand, the peak load of IC160 is much larger than for IC80. Low peak impact loads often indicate that the damage developed in the specimen is higher than for cases with high peak loads and without load drop. Therefore, the energy dissipated for IC80 specimens can be expected to be higher. This result shows an opposite trend in comparison with the results shown in [5]; however, the comparison is not representative due to the large differences in the ply thicknesses used.

Additionally, Fig. 5 summarizes the corresponding values of the dissipated energies for each laminate type and impact energy (calculated according to [7]). As can be observed, little higher dissipated energies are obtained for IC80 laminates. The reason of these differences can be due to larger delaminations and/or larger fibre breakage for IC80. In fact, the damage that can be visually observed in specimens IC80 is clearly greater than in specimens IC160, with evidences of fiber breakage.

Figure 3: Impact load evolution (a) and impact load as a function of the impactor displacement (b) for IC80 laminates.

Figure 4: Impact load evolution (a) and impact load as a function of the impactor displacement (b) for IC160 laminates.

Figure 5: Dissipated energy of each laminate type at different impact energies.

3.2 C-scan inspections

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show a sample of C-scan inspections for IC80 and for IC160 at each impact energy, respectively. As can be observed, significant larger delaminations appear for IC80 at 30 J and 40 J. This result was not expected according to [5], rather smaller delamination areas but higher fibre breakage since larger indentations occurred for these laminates. This result is in agreement with the previous results reported by Saito et al. [6].

Figure 6: Projected delamination areas of IC80 at 20 (a), 30 (b) and 40 J (c).

Figure 7: Projected delamination areas of IC160 at 20 (a), 30 (b) and 40 J (c).

4 CAI RESULTS

The residual compression strengths are summarized in Fig. 8 for both type laminates. As can be observed, there is not a clear effect of the ply thickness for the laminates tested. The residual strength for both laminates follows the same profile.

Figure 8: CAI strength comparison.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results shown, the following points can be concluded:

- For thinner ply laminates, the damage observed by visual inspection is more clear than for thicker ply laminates.
- The first drop of the impact load for thinner ply laminates is higher than for thicker ply laminates, and occurs at higher impactor displacement. This result has been related to the fact that matrix cracking in thinner ply laminates is reduced.
- For intermediate and higher impact energies, the projected delamination area for thinner ply laminates is higher.
- For the material tested, the ply thickness does not have an effect on the compression residual strength.

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